

Exploring Active Galactic Nuclei and Little Red Dots with the Obelisk simulation

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ABSTRACT

1. Milky Way-like dust results

We report here analogs of the figures in the paper published by Astronomy & Astrophysics, but using Milky Way-like dust, for the cases where these were not included. Most of the interpretation presented in the paper is valid also for this dust case (Figs. 3, 4). We only comment on the differences. Fig. 5 shows that in the MW-like case, where extinction is higher, cLRDs avoid the highest dust-to-gas ratios, although the median dust-to-gas ratio of cLRDs is the same as for all AGN with $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$, -2.4 in log space. In Fig. 6 the median AGN A_V using MW-dust for the ‘overm’ case is 2.5, while for the ‘sEdd’ case it’s 2.4. The median A_V for the stellar population is 1.1 (sEdd) and 1.2 (overm). The AGN fraction (Fig. 7) decreases in the MW-like dust when imposing a magnitude cut because both galaxies and AGN are fainter because of the higher extinction. In Fig. 8 the AGN flux is below the y-axis limit for line of sight 3. Fig. 9 shows that, at fixed galaxy and MBH properties, different lines of sight enter the cLRD color selection depending on the dust model adopted.

Fig. 1. Colors for MW-like dust. AGN are defined as sources having $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44}$ erg s^{-1} and $m_{444W} < 28$ (combined galaxy+AGN). cLRDs are defined as the AGN that fall in the UNCOVER color selection (red shaded area). In the left panels we report the fraction of cLRDs over AGN. The expected fraction is between 10 and 20%. In the right panels we report the fraction of cLRDs with $M_{\text{BH}} > 3 \times 10^{-2} M_{\text{star}}$ and with $f_{\text{Edd}} > 0.3$. The yellow points report the colors considering only the AGN emission.

Fig. 2. Magnitudes for the ‘sEdd’ and ‘overm’ models and MW-like dust. The orange triangles and gray circles show separately the flux of AGN and galaxies, when selecting systems with $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and $m_{444W} < 28$ (total flux, summing both AGN and galaxy contribution). The red dots have both of the above, plus the UNCOVER color selection, and show the combined galaxy+AGN flux. We have limited the y-axis to 50 to highlight the relevant parameter space. At 115 and 200 the galaxy is almost always brighter than the AGN, whose contribution increases as the wavelength increases. For the ‘overm’ case some AGN are brighter than the galaxy also at short wavelengths.

Fig. 3. SMILES color selection (shaded red area), with further $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and $m_{444\text{W}} < 28$ (combined galaxy+AGN). The AGN population is defined as meeting only the L_{bol} and $m_{444\text{W}}$ criteria. The yellow points report the colors considering only the AGN emission.

Fig. 4. UNCOVER color selection (shaded red area), with further $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and $m_{444\text{W}} < 28$ (combined galaxy+AGN). The AGN population is defined as meeting only the L_{bol} and $m_{444\text{W}}$ criteria. The yellow points report the colors considering only the AGN emission. Here we use the MW-like extinction curve for the stellar population and the empirical extinction law derived in radio-loud AGN (?) for the AGN.

Fig. 5. Properties of color-selected cLRDs (red) with respect to all AGN with $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ (green) and with further $m444W < 28$ (blue) for MW-like dust. Left: sEdd; right: overm. A clear signature is the specific range in dust column density, N_{dust} , with respect to the global population. Further conditions are the elevated f_{Edd} and ratio between M_{BH} and M_{star} .

Fig. 6. A_V for AGN versus A_V stellar population, for AGN with $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and $m444W < 28$ (first and third rows from top, where we have limited the y-axis to $A_V = 50$) and for systems selected as cLRDs (second and fourth rows from top). We consider MW-like dust for the sEdd and overm models. A_V for the stellar population of systems selected as cLRDs is moderately small with respect to the full extent of the distribution, while A_V for the AGN is significantly skewed towards low values with respect to the global population.

Fig. 7. Left and middle: AGN fraction, defined in terms of AGN bolometric luminosity as a function of galaxy mass. We recall that we have assumed an intrinsic active fraction of unity. Solid lines only require $L_{\text{bol}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$, dotted lines add $m_{444W} < 28$ (galaxy and AGN combined) and dashed lines are for cLRDs (including the same bolometric and m_{444W} cuts). Right: fraction of AGN-dominated sources at F444W as a function of $m_{277W} - m_{444W}$. Above $m_{277W} - m_{444W} > 1.5$ all sources are AGN-dominated.

Fig. 8. Examples of photometry at $z = 6$ showing how different assumptions affect the emergent SEDs. For the same galaxy we show different M_{BH} , f_{Edd} and lines of sight. The galaxy photometry is calculated along the same line of sight as that of the AGN. The SFR is in units of $M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and masses in units of M_{\odot} inside the logarithm. The NIRCAM response for the filters analyzed in this paper is shown in gray.

Fig. 9. Colors for 9 galaxies where we explore how the appearance changes over 12 lines of sight, fixing M_{BH} and f_{Edd} . We show the sEdd and overm cases, for MW-like dust. Each galaxy is shown with a different combination of color and symbol, therefore multiple identical markers indicate different lines of sight for the same galaxy+AGN intrinsic properties. The size of the symbol scales with the AGN optical depth. We show only cases with $m_{444\text{W}} < 28$ (combined galaxy+AGN), but we do not impose any threshold on the AGN luminosity.